

Nudging Urban & Regional Development in Uttarakhand

A Step towards Sustainable Future

**Sustainability Cluster of
School of Engineering, UPES**

Presents

A white paper

On

**Précising the Urbanization
Process**

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Moving towards

SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities

Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable.

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Executive Summary

India is rapidly urbanizing and its population growth for which the Plugin of Urbanization, Conservation, and Economic activities is necessary. In the current decade of the 21st century, the cost of ignoring the development is very high, and keeping that in mind in the 2nd year of the third decade UPES sustainability cluster took this challenge to evaluate the existing master plans and provide the modifications and likely improvements needed in the Process of Development of Urban areas.

The key outcomes of this white paper are as follows: Firstly, to create synergy between urbanization & the natural environment by identifying the 'go' and 'no go' areas at the regional/district level and simultaneously boosting the economy by earmarking the areas for suitable economic engines. Secondly, developing a citywide structure that can accommodate the future needs of transport and land uses. Finally, implementing the master plan proposal and infilling development by pooling the land and financing the infrastructure cost by capturing land value.

We believe that this white paper will serve the policymakers, the decision-makers, planners, and other stakeholders involved in this process. The research will also ease in creation of 'Destination Uttarakhand' by adding incredible urban places, thus tapping the tourism potential.

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Development Planning and Management Processes

To create productive, sustainable, and liveable cities whole urban and regional planning development and management process requires interventions at various scales in terms of pragmatic economic engines, city-wide structure, and infrastructure.

Current Approach	Suitable Approach	Elements
<p>The rigid Masterplan approach with a time horizon of 20 years is unable to accommodate the impacts of technological advances on one hand and it has principle flaw of restricting the play of market forces. The market along with proactive landsue planning is capable of managing location and scale of economic activities. Many of the Masterplans in Uttarakhand are merely 15%-20% implemented due to paucity of land and lack suitable mecahnism.</p>	<p>Level 1: Creation of growth centers and new towns and peripheral development with better transportation linkages through regional planning approach .</p>	<p>Regional Structure</p>
	<p>Level 2: Creation of city wide structure through arterial and sub arterial roads along with trunk infrastructure helping the society by directing the growth in a guided development models through Masterplans.</p>	<p>Economic activities + Linkages</p>
	<p>Level 3: Creation of developed land through land pooling policy. Serviced plots with wide roads, parks, amenities and utilities are valued much higher. The above is possible through zonal plans/ area plans & land pooling policy.</p>	<p>Topography + Landscape</p>
	<p>Urban Form</p>	
	<p>Density + Mix</p>	
	<p>Decongesting City core</p>	
	<p>Serviced Plots</p>	
	<p>Local Infrastructure</p>	
	<p>Parks and amenities</p>	

Plugging-in Economic development Urbanization and Conservation

Case of Doon Valley Region, Uttarakhand

Nestled in the lower Himalayan, doon valley is a unique geographical formation and derives significance from the rich natural heritage that it supports. The valley region is recognized as an eco-sensitive area by MoEF and Supreme Court directed the closures of all mines in the valley (India, 1989). Unplanned urban growth and lack of defining urban areas have led to changes in landcover and encroachment on rivers (Taloor et al., 2020). The valley has the potential, to attract a huge amount of talent and investment by providing regional infrastructure and growth engines like Melbourne (Victoria, 2017).

Map 1: Doon Valley Region

Source: M. Plan 2015-17 Studio work, UPES

To achieve the vision for Melbourne to be a Global city of opportunity and choice a regional structure is conceived that drives productivity, support investments through certainty and creates more jobs.

To maintain competitiveness it is ensured that land supply for commercial and industrial development is adequate, well located and appropriately serviced . The plan also proposes to strengthen the planning and transportation system to decentralized economic activities.

A strong pipeline of investment is underpinning the economic growth and productivity, and greater transport and landuse efficiency.

Settlement Structure + Linkages

Recognize new, integrated land-use and transport strategies in state policy and plans will paint a clear picture at regional level/ district level and push infrastructure-led in next decades

Economic

Defining a new regional structure & settlement hierarchy and simultaneously planning for land requirements of industrial, commercial, and growth centers to meet market demand.

Topography + Landscape

To boost tourism and to maintain a distinct image of destination Uttarakhand special attention is required in terms of conserving the landscape as well as to conceive projects around views and vistas without encroaching the same.

Map 2- Metropolitan Melbourne Structure Plan

Developing a Citywide Structure

Case of Rishikesh, Uttarakhand

The current regime of master planning is proved to be a static long-term planning document and failed miserably to guide future growth and development. Let's understand it through the case of Rishikesh.

Rishikesh masterplan 2011 outcome is visible on the map below. The ill-conceived plan had broadly earmarked the various land use on large tracks of vacant land and a single major transport corridor running through the length of the city (UEP-UDR, 2015). The weekends and vacations witness the crawling traffic and many areas along the Ganga banks remain unexplored. The vast potential of riverfront-led development and financing of infrastructure through land value capture remains untapped (Hart, 2020). The infilling of the buildings in the various land uses proves to be an urban sprawl due to the lack of arterial and sub arterial road structures. The picture becomes further worse when the fire tenders are unable to reach their destination on time. The sewer is allowed to flow freely in the natural drainages. It is surely seems to be an urban chaos and long term neglect in comparison to Hanoi's Masterplan 2030 (Trihamdani et al., 2015).

Map 3: Rishikesh Road Network

Source: B. Plan 2015-19 Studio work, UPES

Urban Form

As compared to the earlier plan the proposed road network will help in creating an urban form that can help in ripping the benefits of the natural resources around the city and improve accessibility. The creation of an overall road structure will decongest the trunk routes & create a better image of the Rishikesh through lively edges, memorable paths with gorgeous landmarks and nodes along Ganga.

Map 4: Rishikesh- Proposed Road Network

Map 5: Hanoi Masterplan 2030

- Low-Density Residential
- Mixed Residential
- Low-Rise Commercial/Retail
- High-Rise Commercial/Mixed-Use

Density + mix

Identifying the densities for development that is low to high benefits in the extrapolation of the infrastructure requirement such as housing, water supply, sewerage, Strom water, telecom infra, etc. Referring to the Hanoi Plan rationale distribution of various activities helps in reducing the conflicts and create synergies among land uses.

Decongesting city core

The creation of new marketplaces and distributing economic activities help to decongest the overcrowded city core. The ghats of Rishikesh are the soul of the city, and the same experience needs to be stretched lower stream to preserve the distinct image.

Hanoi capital city of Vietnam master plan is an extraordinary effort, pushing the city forward by preserving and protecting its natural and cultural assets.

Among the most important feature of the plan is its sustainability strategy. A majority of Hanoi which is full of natural areas and productive agricultural land be permanently protected from further development. The vision also outlines strict preservation of the historic structure and cultural precinct, pre-lined streets, riverbanks, and lakes, and other features like a city-wide structure that will make Hanoi a beautiful and livable city for the generation to come.

Laying Out the basic infrastructure

Case of Arcadia Grant Area Planning Scheme, Dehradun, Uttarakhand

The ever-increasing demand for urban land to meet the needs of the growing urban population has led to the expansion of cities on their periphery. This expansion of cities is very prominent in Uttarakhand and has largely been unplanned.

The existing provision of a zonal development plan aims at defining the extent of various land uses proposed in the zone. In particular contains a provision regarding the division of any sites into plots for the erection of buildings and reservation of land for road open spaces, gardens, recreational grounds, schools, markets, and other public purposes. Zonal plans also failed miserably as the area of the zone is not limited. It is nearly impossible to detail the plans up to the plot level. A promising answer is Land Pooling Scheme on lines of Town Planning Scheme, Gujrat (Ballaney & Patel, 2008).

Map 6: Existing Land Parcels and Road Network- An area of Dehradun

Source: B. Plan 2015-19 Studio work, UPES

Town Planning Scheme of Gujrat merges the existing land holdings and redistributes land in a planned manner after making deductions for street's Right of Way and land for public uses. Land owners derive immense benefits as they receive back developed plots within an organised layout along with all urban services like roads, and other urban infrastructure. The cost for providing urban infrastructure and amenities under such TPS can be financed through Value Capture Financing (VCF) tools such as betterment charges, and sale of reserved plots.

Serviced plots

Reorganization of plots in land pooling-based area planning schemes provides well-serviced plots with valuation even up to 7 times of original land value. It's a step towards higher densities and a better mix of land uses.

Map 7: TPS-90, Vinzol-II, Ahemdabad

Map 6: Proposed Land Pooling Scheme Source: B. Plan 2015-19 Studio work, UPES

Local infrastructure

The Right of Way achieved improves laying out of service lines, provides standard road section with footpath and ample carriageway with tree mix. Underground Utility corridors can all also be constructed which are nowadays adopted by most Smart cities.

Parks and Amenities

The reservation of lands for the parks and other amenities makes the whole living more pleasant and easy. Shopping centers, recreational areas again enhance the value of the neighborhood many times. It also helps in easing the stress of residents by involving in sports and recreational activities.

Actual Model of Area Plan Dudhli Village, Doiwala Road Dehradun.

Source: M. Plan 2016-19 Studio work, UPES

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'Fire Bullet' project developed at university capable of entering the narrow lanes in old city areas in plain regions and pathways of hilly town in a situation of Fire Disaster.

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